

Eumenids of Toranmal Reserve Forest, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract

The Toranmal forest region of Nandurbar district was surveyed for the doctoral research work on Vespoidea wasp taxonomy. During the present investigation, a total of 10 species of eumenid wasps scattered over 7 genera were enumerated. Because of species number, the genus *Delta* erected first on the list with 3 species, followed by genus *Rhynchium* with 2 species while genera *Eumenes*, *Phimenes*, *Orumenoides*, *Antepipona* and *Anterhynchium* were represented by solitary species each.

Keywords: Eumenids, Hymenoptera, Vespidae, Toranmal, Nandurbar.

1. Introduction:

Eumenid wasps (Potter wasps or Mason wasps) belong to the subfamily- Eumeninae. It is an extensively distributed subfamily with species counts about 3,000 distributed over 150 genera (Brothers & Finnamore 1993). The adults have sizes ranging from 7-28 mm with a sessile to strongly petiolate first abdominal segment. They can be easily identified by the following morpho-taxonomic characters: mesoscutum with a posterolateral projection known as parategula; bifid tarsal claws; hind coxa with a longitudinal dorsal folding, and forewing with three submarginal cells. All of them are predators; females often store the narcotised lepidopteran caterpillars into mud nests for their larvae as food provision. The taxonomic and biology studies on Indian potter wasps is scanty and fragmentary. The notable taxonomic work available on Indian eumenids is by Bingham (1897). Van der Vecht (1937, 1959, 1961, 1963, 1981) and Gusenleitner (1996, 1998, 2001, 2006, 2008) immensely contributed to taxonomic

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studies on potter wasps with some important contribution. Significant contributions to the taxonomy of potter wasps of India are by Chhotani & Ray (1975), Ray & Kundu (1985), Gupta (1997, 2003, 2007), Ray (2000, 2003), Lambert & Narendran (2002), Lambert (2004) and Lambert et al. (2007, 2008).

The present endeavor focuses on the investigation of lesser-known taxa with immense ecological importance along with the identification of pollinating wasp species from the Toranmal forest region of Nandurbar district (Fig. 1). It spreads over 41.43 Km² and falls between 21.54 N 74.27 E and 76.30 E co-ordinates and altitude is approximately 1155 meters. It is geographically unique and one of the richest zones with a variety of tropical biota owing to varying combinations of geo-climatic factors at different altitudes.

2. Material and Methods:

The present investigation is based on the collections made during 2023 to 2025. Taxonomic identification followed using authentic research articles, authorized literatures, and monographs (Bingham 1897, Krombein 1978, Das and Gupta 1989, Gupta and Jonathan 2003, Cameron 1900, Girish Kumar 2010, Girish Kumar and Srinivasan 2010).

Fig.01: Study area

3. Results:

The significant uniqueness of eumenids is the modification of the female ovipositor into a venom-injecting device or stinger and their unique habit of making mud nests. Because of their predaceous habits, they have the potential to be effective biological control agents against pests. The range wise distribution of species is shown in (table 1) at the end of systematic account. During the present exertion, a total 10 species, relating to 7 genera of subfamily Eumeninae of family Vespidae wasps have been studied.

1. *Eumenes architectus* Smith, 1858

1858. *Eumenes architectus* Smith, *J. Linn. Soc.*, 3: 20. Female, Male, Syntypes. Type locality Celebes (BMNH).

2010. *Eumenes architectus* Smith: Srinivasan and Girish Kumar, *J. Threatened Taxa*, **2** (12): 1317, 1318.

Diagnosis: Female: Black colour with the subsequent yellow marks: a spot between the antenna, an ambiguous short line behind the eyes at top, a thin intermittent line on the pronotum, a spot on the postscutellum, a narrow line on the apical limits of the petiole and the section of the abdomen. Legs black parti-colored with yellow. Wings fusco-hyaline with coppery reflection. Head, thorax and abdomen finely and closely punctured, unclearly pubescent; clypeus curved, apex intensely emarginated. **Size:** 11 mm.

Forewing length: Female: 8.5 mm.

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Maharashtra, Meghalaya and Sikkim.

Elsewhere: Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Myanmar, South Korea, Thailand.

Remarks: This tiny species confined more to dense vegetation and very sparse in distribution.

2. *Delta pyriforme pyriforme* (Fabricius, 1775)

1775. *Vespa petiolate* Fabricius, *Ent. Syst.*, ii, 278. Syntype, Sex not mentioned, Type locality Malabar, India (BMNH).

1991. *Delta pyriforme pyriforme* (Fabricius): Krombein, *Smithsonian Contrib. Zool.*, 515: 8.

2012. *Delta pyriforme pyriforme* (Fabricius): Girish Kumar and Lambert Kishore, *Uttar Pradesh J. Zool.*, 32 (3): 269-276.

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Diagnosis: Female: Head is yellow, an extensive black band between the eyes on the vertex; occiput black; antenna reddish-brown; pronotum entirely and mesoscutum anteriorly yellow; mesopleuron, metapleuron and legs reddish-brown particolored with black; propodeum reddish-brown with a slim medial vertical black line; the sutures between the scutellum, postscutellum, and propodeum black; petiole and the basal third of the second gastral segment reddish-brown, the former black at the base and with a sub-apical black band, the middle of the later black.

Size: 25-27 mm.

Forewing length: Female: 18.5mm-19.5mm; Male: 17mm-17.5mm.

Distribution: India: Andaman & Nicobar Island, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Orissa, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu Tripura, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Bhutan, Cambodia, China, Hawaii, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Malaysia, Moluccas, Myanmar, Nepal, New Guinea, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam.

Table 1. Distribution of potter wasp species across study region

SI No.	Species	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5
1	<i>Eumenes architectus</i> Smith, 1858	-	+	+	-	-
2	<i>Delta pyriforme pyriforme</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	-	+	+	+	-
3	<i>Delta esuriens</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	-	+	+	+	-
4	<i>Delta conoideum</i> (Gmelin, 1790)	+	+	+	+	+
5	<i>Phimenes flavopictum continentale</i> (Zimmermann, 1931)	-	-	+	-	-
6	<i>Orumenoides edwardsii</i> (de Saussure, 1852)	-	+	-	-	-
7	<i>Antepipona sibilans</i> (Cameron, 1903)	-	+	-	-	-
8	<i>Rhynchium brunneum brunneum</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	-	-	-	+	-
9	<i>Rhynchium carnaticum</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	-	-	-	+	-
10	<i>Anterhynchium (Anterhynchium) abdominale abdominale</i> (Illiger, 1802)	-	+	+	+	-

3. *Delta esuriens* (Fabricius, 1787)

1787. *Vespa esuriens* Fabricius, *Mant. Ins.*, 1: 293. Syntype, Sex not mentioned, Locality India (BMNH).

2010. *Delta esuriens* (Fabricius, 1787): Srinivasan and Girish Kumar, *J. Threatened Taxa*, 2 (12): 1315.

Diagnosis: Female: Head is yellow to light brownish-yellow with unevenly black markings: there is an extensive band on the vertex up to the upper half of frons spreading behind the vertex to the outer side of the temple and to the occiput, a black mark on the anterior tentorial pit reaching up to the sub-antennal suture to the dorsal side of antennal scrobe and touches to the black band on frons and vertex; antennae reddish; petiole light reddish except at base black, at the apex a black band and then a yellow band. **Size:** 14-20 mm. **Male: Size:** 14-17 mm.

Forewing length: Female: 12.5-13 mm; Male: 11.5 mm.

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Delhi, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Orissa, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Australia, Egypt, Indonesia (Borneo, Java), Iran, Iraq, Malaysia, Myanmar, Pakistan, Philippines, Senegal, Sumatra, Sri Lanka and Thailand.

4. *Delta conoideum* (Gmelin, 1790)

1787. *Vespa conica* Fabricius, *Mant. Ins.*, 1-293. Female, Syntype. Type loc. China (BMNH).

2010. *Delta conoideum* (Gmelin): Srinivasan and Girish Kumar, *J. Threatened Taxa*, 2 (12): 1316, 1317.

Diagnosis: Female: Head is yellow except for mandibles and antenna is reddish, a broad slanting band across the apex between the upper portion of the eyes black; thorax dark red with black spots on mesoscutum, metapleuron and median area of propodeum, pro-pleuron entirely black; legs pale reddish; gaster dark red with the base of the second tergite and a little crosswise medially intervallic band on its middle above black. Head above the antenna and thorax closely and lightly punctured; clypeus pyriform, its apex truncate; gaster smooth and shining with the surface minutely aciculate. **Size:** 23-26mm.

Male: The body is thinner and the terminal antennal segments are curved. **Size:** 18-22 mm.

Forewing length: Female: 17.5-19 mm; Male: 16-17 mm.

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, and Uttar Pradesh.

Elsewhere: Arabia, China, Malaysia, Myanmar, Pakistan, Sri Lanka and Thailand.

Remarks: Most abundant of all other eumenids during present study. Found perching on floral vegetation in search of lepidopteran larvae. They built their pot-shaped mud nest and provision it with lepidopteran larvae. Mud collection was seen profoundly near streams in post monsoon season.

5. *Phimenes flavopictum continentale* (Zimmermann, 1931)

1931. *Eumenes arcuata continentalis* Zimmermann, *Zeitschr. Morph. Oek. Tiere*, **22**: 203, Female, Male, Syntypes, Type Loc. Sikkim (ZMB).

2010. *Phimenes flavopictum continentale* (Zimmermann): Srinivasan and Girish Kumar, *J. Threatened Taxa*, **2** (12): 1317, 1318.

Diagnosis: Female: Body is all black. The yellow markings are as follows: Clypeus, space between the antennae, inner orbit, a line behind the eyes, front of pronotum, mesoscutum with two curved spots and two parallel longitudinal lines, tegula with a broad outer border, a spot on either side of scutellum, a broad vertical mark on mesopleuron, sides of the dorsum of propodeum (with median Maltese cross-shaped black mark), two small lateral spots at the base of the petiole, two about the middle and a sub-apical band of the same above, two large spots near the base of the second gastral segment, two-minute lateral spots on second gastral sternites. **Size:** 24-26 mm.

Male: Besides the customary sexual dimorphism of vespidae structure similar to female in general appearance but slighter, with last abdominal segment entirely black. **Size:** 19-20 mm.

Forewing length: Female: 17-18 mm; Male: 16 mm.

Distribution: India: Arunachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: China, Hong Kong, Indonesia (Bangka, Sumatra, Sunda), Malaysia, Myanmar, Singapore, Thailand (Siam).

6. *Oreumenoides edwardsii* (de Saussure, 1852)

1852. *Eumenes edwardsii* de Saussure, *Mon. Guep. Sol.* P. **60**, Female, Syntype, Type loc. Les Indes-Orientales, Bombay (MP).

2011. *Oreumenoides edwardsii* (de Saussure): Girish Kumar, *Rec. zool. Surv. India* : **111** (1): 11-16.

Diagnosis: Female: Body ferruginous red with yellow and black markings. Yellow markings as follows: at the clypeus, a triangular mark on inter-antennal space, the inner margin of the lower eye extends up to the ocular sinus, a slender line on the external margin of the eye, a spot on the ventral side of the antennal attachment, a short line on the middle of the pronotum, a spot on tegula apically, parategula, the lower half of metanotum, two spots posterolaterally on third gastral tergite, a narrow band on second gastral sternite apically. **Size:** 14-16 mm.

Male: Colour similar to that of female except the labrum yellow and mandible yellowish brown in the males; last antennal segment minute, not coiled apically; parameral spine with moderately large hairs. **Size:** 14.5 mm. **Forewing length:** Female: 11 mm; Male 10.5 mm.

Distribution: India: Delhi, Bihar, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Pondicherry, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal.

7. *Antepipona sibilans* (Cameron, 1903)

1903. *Odynerus sibilans* Cameron, 129. Type specimen : Male; Type Locality : Barrackpore; Type Location : Oxford University Museum, Oxford.

2014. *Antepipona sibilans* Cameron: Kumar and Sharma, *Journal on New Biological Reports*, **3** (3): 239.

Diagnosis: Female: Body is black, Following are yellow mandible except at teeth; a band on upper margin of clypeus; scape except a black line on upper surface toward apex; across front, with exception of inter-antennal space and two black spots, which start from antennal toruli and directed obliquely upward; a large stain on temple; a broad band on dorsal surface of pronotum; first tergite with a large apical band together with two large lateral spots; second tergite with two large lateral spots at base, and often combined with an apical end; third tergite with a narrow band, but strongly enlarged at sides. **Size:** 6.0 mm. **Forewing length:** Female: 5.5 mm

Distribution: India: Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Odisha, Pondicherry, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Nepal and Pakistan.

8. *Rhynchium brunneum brunneum* (Fabricius, 1793)

1793. *Vespa brunnea* Fabricius, *Ent. Syst.*, **2**: 264. Syntype, sex not mentioned. Type Locality Tranquebariae, India (BMNH).

2010. *Rhynchium brunneum* (Fabricius): Srinivasan and Girish Kumar, *J. Threatened Taxa*, **2** (12): 1319, 1320.

Diagnosis: Female: Brownish red body with the following black marks: a spot between both the antennae, a vertical line on lower frons, surrounding ocelli, occiput, a large triangular mark in anterior of meso-scutum, with a crosswise line lengthwise its apex, pro pleuron, mesopleuron, the middle and adjacent sides of propodeum, basal two thirds of the first and the lower half of second tergite. Legs brownish-red with spotted black markings. The wings are hyaline, deeper and darker towards base. **Size:** 17-20 mm.

Male: Structure similar to female in general appearance with the exception of clypeus and scape in front light fulvous red to bright yellow. **Size:** 12 mm. **Forewing length:** Female: 16.5 mm; Male: 11.5 mm.

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Sikkim, Tripura, Uttarakhand and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Afghanistan, Indonesia, Iran, Malaysia, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka and Thailand.

9. *Rhynchium carnaticum* (Fabricius, 1798)

1798. *Vespa carnatica* Fabricius, *Suppl. Entomol. Syst.*, p. **261**. Syntype, sex not mentioned, Tranquebariae, India (UZMC).

2013. *Rhynchium carnaticum*: Kumar & Sharma, *Rec. zool. Surv. India* : **113** (2): 110.

Diagnosis: Female: Brownish red body with the following black markings: a spot between interantennal space, a vertical line on lower frons, surrounding the ocelli, occiput, a triangular mark in front of mesoscutum, a transverse line along its apex, pleural sides of propleuron, epicnemium, propodeum in the middle, first tergite at its basal area, at the base of second tergite, in between first and second sternite, base of third sternite. Legs brownish red with variegated black markings. The black markings in the body are highly reduced as compared to *R. brunneum brunneum*. Wings yellowish hyaline, apical margin of forewing lightly infumated. **Size:** 14-15 mm.

Forewing length: Female: 14.5-15 mm.

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Indonesia, Pakistan, Sri Lanka.

10. *Anterhynchium (Anterhynchium) abdominale abdominale* (Illiger, 1802)

1802. *Vespa abdominalis* Illiger, *Magaz. Insektenk*, **1**: 192.

1963. *Anterhynchium abdominale*; van der Vecht, *Zool. Verh., Leiden*, **60**: 75, fig. 5e (forewing) (Calcutta, Walayar forest, Cinchona, Ceylon).

Diagnosis: Female: Head and middle segment are black; the third segment is dull orange-red with particolored black patterns on the following parts: the basal segment with a transverse black apical band, second abdominal tergite with a transverse black spot in the middle of its apical margin, the remaining segments usually orange-red except last segment black, gastral sternites usually orange-red with varying degree of black color except last segment entirely black. The brown coloration is as follows: ventral side of the antenna and tarsal segments. Wings dark fuscous with purple reflections. **Size:** 14-14.5 mm.

Fore wing length: Female: 13.5-14 mm.

Distribution: India: Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh, and West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Myanmar, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka.

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